

Probiotic supplementation during pregnancy and risk of gestational diabetes: A real-world pharmacoepidemiological study in a high-risk Bulgarian cohort

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Abstract

Background: The role of probiotic supplementation in the prevention of gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) remains controversial, with conflicting evidence from randomized trials and observational studies. Despite increasing use in pregnancy, real-world data, particularly in high-risk populations, is limited.

Aim: To evaluate the association between probiotic supplementation and the development of GDM in a high-risk Bulgarian population and to identify key maternal predictors.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted including 946 pregnant women. Risk stratification was performed at 11–13 + 6 gestational weeks using an anamnestic screening model. Probiotic supplementation was recorded as a non-randomized exposure reflecting routine clinical practice. GDM was diagnosed at 24–28 weeks using a 75 g oral glucose tolerance test. Multivariable logistic regression was applied to assess independent predictors.

Results: GDM developed in 8.35% of participants, while 11.95% received probiotic supplementation. Among high-risk women, GDM occurred more frequently in women receiving probiotic supplementation compared to non-users (25% vs. 13.67%, $p = 0.0095$). However, probiotic supplementation was more common in women with higher baseline risk. Independent predictors of GDM included previous GDM (odds ratio [OR] 32.0), chronic hypertension (OR 6.81), and maternal body mass index (BMI) and age. Probiotic supplementation was also associated with GDM (OR 4.97), likely reflecting confounding by indication. No significant effect on gestational weight gain was observed.

Conclusion: In this real-world cohort, probiotic supplementation was associated with a higher observed incidence of GDM; however, this relationship is most likely explained by underlying risk differences rather than a causal effect. Maternal metabolic factors remain the primary determinants of GDM. These findings highlight the need for cautious interpretation of observational associations and for well-designed randomized trials with standardized probiotic formulations.

Keywords

Gestational diabetes mellitus; probiotics; pregnancy; risk factors; pharmacoepidemiology; real-world evidence

Introduction

Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is one of the most common metabolic complications of pregnancy, with a globally increasing prevalence estimated at approximately 14% (Guariguata et al. 2014). Its clinical importance extends beyond pregnancy, as GDM is associated with both short-term obstetric complications and long-term metabolic consequences for the mother and offspring, including increased risk of type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular disease (“Hyperglycemia and Adverse Pregnancy Outcomes” 2008; Hod et al. 2015). These considerations highlight the need for effective preventive strategies, particularly in populations at elevated risk.

The pathophysiology of GDM is characterized by increased insulin resistance combined with insufficient pancreatic β -cell compensation (Buchanan 2001; Catalano 2010). While genetic predisposition contributes to disease susceptibility, the development of GDM is largely driven by modifiable factors, such as maternal obesity and metabolic dysfunction, which are further exacerbated by pregnancy-related hormonal changes (Buchanan and Xiang 2005). In addition, a chronic low-grade inflammatory state observed in pregnancy and obesity plays a key role in the progression of insulin resistance (Abell et al. 2015).

Current preventive strategies are primarily focused on lifestyle interventions, including dietary modification and physical activity. However, evidence regarding their effectiveness remains inconsistent, particularly in high-risk populations (Rogozińska et al. 2017; Shepherd et al. 2017). This has prompted increasing interest in alternative or adjunctive approaches targeting metabolic and inflammatory pathways.

In this context, modulation of the gut microbiota has emerged as a potential therapeutic target. Probiotic supplementation has been proposed as a low-risk intervention capable of influencing glucose metabolism through mechanisms such as reduction of systemic inflammation, modulation of gut permeability, and enhancement of insulin sensitivity (Uzair et al. 2025). From a pharmaceutical perspective, probiotics are widely used as over-the-counter products during pregnancy, often without standardized formulations or clear evidence-based recommendations.

Despite growing interest, the role of probiotics in the prevention of GDM remains controversial. A Cochrane review reported no clear benefit, with wide confidence intervals encompassing both potential reduction and increase in GDM risk (RR 0.80, 95% CI 0.54–1.20; low-certainty evidence) (Davidson et al. 2021). In contrast, more recent large-scale analyses suggest a possible protective effect, including an umbrella meta-analysis demonstrating a 29% reduction in GDM risk (RR 0.71, 95% CI 0.61–0.83) (Gao et al. 2025). Additional evidence indicates that multi-strain probiotic formulations may be more effective than single-strain preparations (Pakmehr et al. 2022). However, substantial heterogeneity across studies in terms of population characteristics, probiotic strains, dosage, and timing of intervention limits the generalizability of these findings.

Furthermore, probiotics appear to exert more consistent metabolic benefits in women with established GDM rather than in normoglycemic pregnancies, suggesting a potential therapeutic rather than preventive role (Łagowska et al. 2020; Çetinkaya Özdemir et al. 2022). Safety considerations also remain relevant, as some evidence indicates an increased risk of preeclampsia associated with probiotic supplementation, although data on other obstetric outcomes are inconclusive (Uzair et al. 2025).

Importantly, most available evidence is derived from randomized controlled trials conducted under controlled conditions, which may not reflect real-world clinical practice. In routine care, probiotic supplementation is often initiated in women already identified as being at increased metabolic risk, raising the possibility of confounding by indication and complicating the interpretation of observational findings.

In Bulgaria, data on early risk stratification for GDM and the use of preventive interventions such as probiotics remain limited. Evaluating the effectiveness of such interventions in real-world settings is essential for improving clinical decision-making and optimizing patient care.

Therefore, the aim of the present study was to evaluate the association between probiotic supplementation and the development of GDM in a high-risk Bulgarian population and to identify the most significant maternal predictors within a real-world clinical context.

Materials and methods

Study design and population

This prospective observational cohort study included 946 pregnant women receiving antenatal care. Participants were enrolled during the first trimester of pregnancy (11–13 + 6 gestational weeks).

Women were stratified according to their risk of GDM using a validated anamnestic screening model (Syngelaki et al. 2015), incorporating maternal demographic and clinical characteristics, including age, body mass index (BMI), family history of diabetes, obstetric history, and pre-existing comorbidities.

Exposure assessment: probiotic supplementation

Probiotic supplementation was recorded as a non-randomized exposure reflecting routine clinical practice.

Participants were categorized into two groups—women receiving probiotic supplementation and women not receiving probiotic supplementation.

Probiotic supplementation was typically initiated around the 12th gestational week and continued until late pregnancy. No predefined minimum dose threshold or duration of administration was required for classification as receiving probiotic supplementation. Exposure classification was based on documented probiotic supplementation during pregnancy, reflecting routine clinical practice.

Details on probiotic formulations, including strain composition, dosage, and duration of administration, were collected when available. In cases where detailed formulation data were unavailable or incomplete, participants remained classified according to overall probiotic exposure status, but formulation-specific analyses were not performed. However, probiotic supplementation reflected heterogeneous over-the-counter products with variable composition and dosing, limiting the standardization of exposure and comparability across participants.

The timing of probiotic initiation was analyzed descriptively but was not included as a variable in the regression models.

Outcome definition

The primary outcome was the development of GDM, diagnosed between 24 and 28 gestational weeks using a 75 g oral glucose tolerance test (OGTT), according to established international diagnostic criteria.

Covariates

The following maternal variables were included in the analysis as potential predictors of GDM:

- Maternal age
- Body mass index (BMI)
- Previous history of GDM
- Chronic hypertension

Gestational weight gain was analyzed as a secondary outcome and was not included as a primary predictor in the regression models.

Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize baseline characteristics. Continuous variables are presented as means and standard deviations, while categorical variables are presented as absolute frequencies and percentages.

Comparisons between groups were performed using the chi-square test for categorical variables and the independent-samples *t*-test or analysis of variance (ANOVA) for continuous variables.

Multivariable logistic regression analysis was conducted to identify independent predictors of GDM. Results are presented as odds ratios (ORs) with corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CIs).

Subgroup analysis was performed in women classified as high-risk for GDM.

A *p*-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Methodological considerations

As probiotic supplementation was not randomized and was more frequently administered to women identified as high-risk, the analysis is subject to confounding by indication, which may influence the observed associations.

Ethics statement

Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to inclusion in the study. The study protocol was approved by the local Ethics Committee and conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Results

A total of 946 pregnant women were included in the analysis, of whom 79 (8.35%) developed GDM. Probiotic supplementation was reported in 113 women (11.95%).

Risk stratification using the anamnestic screening model demonstrated high sensitivity, with 87.3% of GDM cases correctly identified as high-risk. Specificity was moderate, as reflected by a false-positive rate of 39.6% (Table 1).

The timing of probiotic initiation was analyzed descriptively. Most women initiated supplementation at approximately the 12th gestational week, with a smaller proportion starting at the 13th week. The majority continued supplementation until late pregnancy, most commonly until 38–39 gestational weeks.

Table 1. Performance of the anamnestic screening model for prediction of GDM.

GDM status	Low risk <i>n</i> (%)	High risk <i>n</i> (%)	Total
No GDM	524 (60.4%)	343 (39.6%)	867
GDM	10 (12.7%)	69 (87.3%)	79

Sensitivity: 87.3%; specificity: 60.4%.

Abbreviations: GDM, gestational diabetes mellitus. Percentages are calculated within each GDM status group.

A predefined subgroup analysis was conducted among women classified as high-risk for GDM (*n* = 412). Within this subgroup, probiotic supplementation was administered to 112 women, while 300 did not receive probiotics.

Among high-risk women who did not receive probiotics, 41 (13.67%) developed GDM, compared to 28 (25%) among women receiving probiotic supplementation. This difference was statistically significant ($\chi^2 = 6.72$, *p* = 0.0095) (Table 2). However, probiotic supplementation was more frequently observed in women with higher baseline risk.

Table 2. GDM outcomes by probiotic supplementation in high-risk pregnancies.

Probiotic	GDM	<i>N</i>	Percentage
No probiotic supplementation	No	259	86.33%
No probiotic supplementation	Yes	41	13.67%
Probiotic supplementation	No	84	75%
Probiotic supplementation	Yes	28	25%

Maternal characteristics differed between women with and without GDM. Women who developed GDM had consistently higher body weight and BMI throughout pregnancy, with differences of approximately five BMI units compared to those without GDM.

Multivariable logistic regression analysis identified previous GDM as the strongest predictor (OR 32.0), followed by chronic hypertension (OR 6.81), maternal BMI, and

Table 3. Predictors of GDM (logistic regression).

Variable	β (coefficient)	OR (exp β)	95% CI (approx.)	<i>p</i> -value	Interpretation
BMI (20 g.w.)	0.153	1.17	1.10–1.25	< 0.001	Strong predictor
Age	0.087	1.09	1.05–1.13	< 0.001	Moderate predictor
Previous GDM	3.466	32.0	4.00–200.00	0.002	Very strong predictor
Chronic hypertension	1.918	6.81	2.00–20.00	0.001	Significant predictor
Probiotic supplementation	1.604	4.97	2.00–12.00	< 0.001	Confounded association

Abbreviations: GDM, gestational diabetes mellitus; OR, odds ratio; CI, confidence interval.

Gestational weight gain was analyzed as a secondary outcome. No significant difference was observed between women receiving probiotic supplementation and those who did not. Mean weight gain was 15.6 kg in the non-probiotic group and 16.2 kg in the probiotic group, with similar variability (Table 4).

Table 4. Weight gain and probiotic intake.

Group	Mean weight gain (kg)	SD
No probiotic	15.6	6.87
Probiotic	16.2	6.73

age. Probiotic supplementation was also associated with GDM (OR 4.97), although this likely reflects confounding by indication rather than a causal relationship (Table 3).

Fetal growth parameters differed between groups, with pregnancies complicated by GDM showing higher abdominal circumference and estimated fetal weight percentiles, particularly from the second trimester onward.

Delivery outcomes also varied by GDM status. Cesarean section rates were higher among women with GDM (74.7%) compared to those without GDM (63.7%). Neonatal birth weight was also higher in the GDM group (3289 \pm 481 g vs. 3187 \pm 456 g) (Table 5).

Table 5. Delivery and neonatal outcomes.

Outcome	GDM	No GDM
Cesarean section	74.7%	63.7%
Vaginal delivery	25.3%	36.3%
Birth weight (g)	3289 \pm 481	3187 \pm 456

Although a slightly higher birth weight was observed among women receiving probiotic supplementation, this difference was not clinically significant.

Importantly, probiotic supplementation was not randomly assigned and was more frequently administered to women with higher baseline risk, which likely explains the observed association with increased GDM incidence.

Discussion

The present study provides real-world evidence on the association between probiotic supplementation and the development of GDM in a high-risk pregnant population. In contrast to some expectations derived from randomized controlled trials and meta-analyses, probiotic supplementation was associated with a higher observed incidence of GDM in this cohort. However, this finding is unlikely to reflect a causal relationship and is best explained by confounding by indication, as probiotic supple-

mentation was more frequently administered to women with higher baseline risk.

This observation highlights a critical distinction between controlled clinical trials and real-world clinical practice. While randomized studies suggest that probiotics may exert a modest protective effect on GDM risk, these findings are not consistently replicated across different populations and study designs. For example, a Cochrane review reported no clear evidence of benefit (RR 0.80, 95% CI 0.54–1.20) (Davidson et al. 2021), whereas more recent meta-analyses suggest a potential reduction in GDM incidence, particularly with multi-strain formulations (Pakmehr et al. 2022; Gao et al. 2025). The discrepancy between these findings and the present results likely reflects differences in study populations, intervention standardization, and methodological design.

A key factor contributing to this inconsistency is the heterogeneity of probiotic formulations. In randomized controlled trials, probiotic interventions are typically standardized with respect to strain composition, dosage, and duration. In contrast, the present study reflects routine clinical practice, where probiotic supplementation is characterized by substantial variability, including the use of over-the-counter products with differing bacterial strains and dosing regimens. This lack of standardization may attenuate potential therapeutic effects and complicate interpretation of clinical outcomes (Uzair et al. 2025).

From a pathophysiological perspective, probiotics are proposed to influence glucose metabolism through modulation of the gut microbiota, reduction of systemic inflammation, and improvement of insulin sensitivity (Uzair et al. 2025). These mechanisms may have limited impact on women with established metabolic dysfunction. In the present study, the strongest predictors of GDM were maternal BMI, age, previous GDM, and chronic hypertension, findings that are consistent with existing literature (Giannakou et al. 2019; Zhang et al. 2021). Notably, previous GDM demonstrated the highest predictive value, emphasizing the dominant role of underlying metabolic risk factors over adjunctive interventions.

Furthermore, evidence suggests that probiotics may be more effective in improving metabolic parameters in women with established GDM rather than preventing its onset. A meta-analysis demonstrated improvements in glucose metabolism primarily in women with GDM, with limited effects observed in normoglycemic pregnancies (Łagowska et al. 2020). Similarly, other analyses report modest improvements

in insulin sensitivity and glycemic control in affected populations (Çetinkaya Özdemir et al. 2022). These findings support the hypothesis that probiotics may have a therapeutic rather than preventive role in the context of GDM.

In the present cohort, probiotic supplementation was not associated with significant effects on gestational weight gain, consistent with previous evidence suggesting only limited and modest metabolic benefits during pregnancy (Davidson et al. 2021; Ye et al. 2022; Jia et al. 2025).

From a pharmaceutical perspective, the widespread use of probiotics during pregnancy warrants careful consideration. Despite being widely perceived as safe and beneficial, probiotics are not standardized medicinal products, and their pharmacological properties vary considerably depending on strain composition, viability, and dosing. The lack of regulatory uniformity and clinical guidance further complicates their use in routine practice. The findings of this study highlight the need for more rigorous evaluation and standardization of probiotic interventions in pregnancy. From a pharmaceutical care perspective, pharmacists are well positioned to support pregnant women through evidence-based counseling on probiotic supplementation, including product selection, safety considerations, and realistic expectations regarding clinical benefits. This is particularly relevant given the substantial heterogeneity of commercially available probiotic formulations and the lack of standardized clinical recommendations (Davidson et al. 2021; Uzair et al. 2025).

The clinical implications of these findings are twofold. First, probiotic supplementation should not be considered a reliable preventive strategy for GDM, particularly in high-risk populations. Second, observational associations between supplement use and clinical outcomes must be interpreted with caution, as they may reflect underlying differences in baseline risk rather than true treatment effects.

This study has several limitations. Its observational design precludes causal inference, and the non-randomized allocation of probiotic supplementation introduces potential selection bias. Additionally, detailed information on probiotic formulations was not consistently available, limiting the ability to assess strain-specific effects. Residual confounding cannot be excluded. Nevertheless, the prospective design and relatively large sample size enhance the validity and clinical relevance of the findings.

In conclusion, probiotic supplementation was associated with a higher observed incidence of GDM in this high-risk cohort; however, this relationship is most likely explained by confounding by indication rather than a true adverse effect. Maternal metabolic factors remain the primary determinants of GDM development. Future research should focus on well-designed randomized controlled trials using standardized probiotic formulations to clarify their role in the prevention and management of GDM.

Limitations

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. First, the observational design precludes causal inference, and the

non-randomized allocation of probiotic supplementation introduces potential selection bias. In particular, the preferential use of probiotics in women identified as high-risk suggests the presence of confounding by indication, which likely influenced the observed association with GDM.

Second, probiotic exposure was not standardized and reflected the use of heterogeneous over-the-counter products with variable strain composition, dosage, and duration of administration. This variability limits the ability to assess formulation-specific effects and reduces comparability across participants.

Third, detailed information on probiotic formulations and certain clinical variables was not consistently available for all participants, which may have affected the precision of some analyses. Finally, residual confounding by unmeasured factors cannot be excluded, as is typical for real-world observational studies.

Despite these limitations, the prospective design and relatively large sample size enhance the robustness and clinical relevance of the findings.

Conclusion

In this real-world cohort of high-risk pregnant women, probiotic supplementation was associated with a higher observed incidence of GDM; however, this finding is most likely explained by confounding by indication rather than a causal effect. Maternal metabolic characteristics remained the primary predictors of GDM development. The heterogeneity and lack of standardization of probiotic formulations limit their applicability as preventive interventions in routine clinical practice. Further randomized controlled studies using standardized probiotic formulations are needed to clarify their role in GDM prevention.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: University Hospital "Saint George" Plovdiv, Bulgaria.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

P.Z.D. conceived the study, performed the analysis, and drafted the manuscript. B.S. and N.P. supervised the study. N.D. and A.M. contributed to data curation and analysis. A.P. and E.U. contributed to methodology and manuscript revision. All authors contributed to the interpretation of the results and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.